

SORSE Workshops: **FAIR4RS**

17 and 19 November 2020

Collaborative notes

Slides and notes(not

Slides:

https://docs.google.com/presentation/d/1nDZcVAO_kLe-610aYsWoKJiyRB71nRHPnu05GmDSq2l/edit#slide=id.gab40f73f94_0_0

Collaborative notes (this document): <https://tinyurl.com/y6b24eyz>

Useful links

[RDA group page](#), [GitHub repository](#)

Session2 November 19th

Agenda

17:00 CEST	SORSE intro Goal of the workshop FAIR & FAIR software intro with live activity
18:00	Break
18:15	FAIR4RS introduction to the Working Group Update of the 4 subgroups work Questions and answers
18:50	Break
19:00- 20:00	Breakout groups <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. What does interoperability mean for software? 2. What does reusability mean for software? 3. How would you want to get credit for making your software

	<p>FAIR?</p> <p>Report back</p> <p>Next steps</p>
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Participants

- **Add your name, institution, country, member, activities with the group**
Click Join Group to become a member
<https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/fair-4-research-software-fair4rs-wg>
This is the preferred way for communications with the community.

Name	Institution	Country	FAIR4RS WG member (YES/NO)	Subgroup activity
Neil Chue Hong	Software Sustainability Institute/ University of Edinburgh	United Kingdom	YES	Subgroup 4
Alejandra Gonzalez-Beltran	Scientific Computing Department, Science and Technology Facilities Council, UK Research and Innovation	United Kingdom	YES	
Leyla Garcia Castro	ZB MED Information Centre for Life Sciences	Germany	YES	Subgroup 2 and 4
Dominic Kempf	Scientific Software Center, IWR, Heidelberg University	Germany	NO	
Daniel Garijo	Information Sciences Institute, University of Southern California	US	Yes	
Renato Alves	European Molecular Biology Laboratory, Heidelberg	Germany	NO	
Daniel S. Katz	University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign	USA	YES	1 and 3
Carlos Martinez	Netherlands eScience center	Netherlands	Yes	3
Jean-Noël Grad	University of Stuttgart	Germany	NO	

Mary Chester-Kadwell	University of Cambridge	United Kingdom	NO	
Christine Rogers	McGill University	Canada	NO	
Maria Luiza CAmpos	Federal University of Rio de Janeiro	Brazil	NO	
Niket Agrawal	TU Delft	Netherlands	No	
Fotis Psomopoulos	Institute of Applied Biosciences, Centre for Research and Technology Hellas	Greece	Yes	
Zuzanna Zagrodzka	University of Sheffield	United Kingdom	No	
Maurits Kok	TU Delft	Netherlands	No	
Tamora James	Centre for Environmental Modelling and Computation, University of Leeds	United Kingdom	No	
Joao Moreira	U. Twente	Netherlands	no	
Anna-Lena Lamprecht	Utrecht University	Netherlands	yes	3, 4

Notes

Breakout Rooms

- Participants change their name to be assigned to their room.

Time		Description	Facilitator (s1)
30	10:05	Breakout groups: (Participants change their name to be assigned to their room.) <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. What does interoperability mean for software? 2. What does reusability mean for software? 3. How would you want to get credit for making your software FAIR? 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Leyla 2. Carlos 3. Neil

Next steps - community engagement plans

- What other initiatives should we collaborate or connect to? What initiatives and organizations should be contacted for consultation in your community?

Please describe and add links

Organisation/initiative name	Contact details
in Neuroscience: INCF (e.g. via Malin who was here Tues) -Christine	incf.org/ Malin Sandstrom
W3C DCAT vocabulary - we are discussing if adding Software as part of the vocabulary	Alejandra (alejandra.gonzalez-beltran@stfc.ac.uk)

- What 2021 events would be a good location for FAIR4RS principles consultation?

Event name	+upvoters
Collaborations Workshop 2021 (which already has a FAIR for software theme)	+1 Alejandra
AGU Fall Meeting 2021 (which has had a strong push for FAIR)	
More SORSE events	+1
Local RSE events (DE-, NL-, nordic, etc) (or is SORSE enough?)	
“Bring your own seminar” - if we had a slide set and instructions that we could deliver at our own organisations	+1

- What types of materials would be helpful to facilitate discussions about FAIR 4 Research Software, other than the draft FAIR4RS principles?

Materials	Contributor +upvoters
Decision trees or flowcharts	+1, +Daniel G
Which documents where you want community feedback. How to contribute?	+Daniel G
Suggestion: Publicize the timeline (and links) for Input on Twitter	
Short set of slides that people can use in their own orgs	+1+1
List of incentives to implement FAIR	+1+1

Feedback

Thanks for joining us!!!

Let us know your thoughts of this session, we are looking to improve.

1. Did we meet your expectations?

Yes, I have come away with a basic understanding of FAIR as it might apply to software and now aware of what FAIR2RS is.

Yes! Thanks for organising!!

I'm not sure what I was expecting but I found it an informative, well-run and interesting session.

2. Did you feel comfortable during the workshop?

Absolutely.

3. What was the most memorable thing from your experience with us?

Learning FAIR principles by answering questions

Brainstorming ideas about FAIR software via menti.com.

4. Is there anything else you would like us to know about your experience?

I liked the short full-participant discussion rather than the individual breakouts because it was good to consider all the different questions, and with small breakout rooms it's often difficult to get a good discussion going but many people (myself included!) are quiet.

I was a bit apprehensive about the breakout groups so I was happy we stayed as a single group, also good to hear all of the different questions and discussion. I liked the use of collaborative docs for gathering responses.

5. What can be improved for the next session?

The 2 time slots were both kind of awkward (central Europe). (+1 for UK) +1

I really liked the tables in Neil's session for providing feedback and would suggest other breakout sessions should follow the same format. (+1)

Menti is really nice, but it could be combined with discussion

Session1 November 17th

Agenda

8:00	SORSE intro Goal of the workshop FAIR & FAIR software intro with live activity
9:00	Break
9:15	FAIR4RS introduction to the Working Group Update of the 4 subgroups work Questions and answers
9:50	Break
10:00	Breakout groups <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 4. What does interoperability mean for software? 5. What does reusability mean for software? 6. How would you want to get credit for making your software FAIR? Report back Next steps

Participants

- **Add your name, institution, country, member, activities with the group**
 Click [Join Group](#) to become a member
<https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/fair-4-research-software-fair4rs-wg>
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Name	Institution	Country	FAIR4RS WG member (YES/NO)	Subgroup activity
<i>Paula Andrea Martínez</i>		<i>Australia</i>	YES	1, 2, 3, 4
Stephan Janosch	Max Planck Institute of Molecular Cell Biology and Genetics (MPI-CBG)	Germany	NO	
Matthias Liffers	Australian Research Data Commons	Australia	Yes	SG1
Axel Loewe	Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (KIT)	Germany	YES	-
Onder Babur	Eindhoven University of Technology	Netherlands	NO	
Malin Sandström	INCF, Karolinska Institute	Sweden	Yes, recently	Don't know yet
Rouven Schabinger	Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (KIT) / re3data	Germany	YES	
Cunliang Geng	Netherlands eScience Center	Netherlands	No	
Morane Gruenpeter	Inria, Software Heritage	France	Yes	1,3
Markus Konkol	University of Twente, ITC	NL/GER	No	-
Teri Forey	Wellcome Trust	UK	No	
Fotis Psomopoulos	Institute of Applied Biosciences, Centre for Research and Technology Hellas	Greece	Yes	

Carlos Martinez	Netherlands eScience Center	Netherlands	Yes	
Anna-Lena Lamprecht	Utrecht University	Netherlands	Yes	3,4

Notes

- How can one identify an appropriate registry / repository for code? (Stephan Janosch)
 - Re3data: browse by content type! (feel free to give feedback and contact info@re3data.org , Rouven Schabinger -sry, couldn't stay for the meeting)
 - Basic drilldown with contentTypes[]=Source code
 - [https://www.re3data.org/search?query=&contentTypes\[\]=Source%20code](https://www.re3data.org/search?query=&contentTypes[]=Source%20code)
 -

The easy way: use one of the existing efforts, eg re3data, swmath, fairsharing, NITRC, G-Node's GIN, Science Gateways Catalogue, Imperial College London Research Software directory (beta), the Canadian Open Neuroscience platform (CONP), ModelDB (specialised on computational models), open source brain (www.opensourcebrain.org), HBP's EBRAINS (I have lots of neuro examples if that is relevant /Malin)

- Relevant workshop on RS: <https://sorse.github.io/programme/workshops/event-017/> with 3 documents for input:
 - [People questions](#)
 - [Infrastructure questions](#)
 - [Policy questions](#)
- Is software sharing really a new idea? Isn't this something which already existed in industry for a long time?
 - In part, yes -- industry has worked with package managers for a very long time, but they do not interoperate between different programming languages
 - In part, yes -- different industries had different standards for sharing software. It is only now that collaboration is becoming important.
 - When I (Malin) was little in the 80's, there was extensive informal sharing of software via disks (there were networks of people supporting this by copying and sharing) - less industry involvement but they must have known.
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Breakout Rooms

- Participants change their name to be assigned to their room.

Time		Description	Facilitator (s1)
30	10:05	Breakout groups: (Participants change their name to be assigned to their room.) <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 4. What does interoperability mean for software? 5. What does reusability mean for software? 6. How would you want to get credit for making your software FAIR? 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Fotis 2. Carlos 3. Paula

Next steps - community engagement plans

- What other initiatives should we collaborate or connect to? What initiatives and organizations should be contacted for consultation in your community?

Please describe and add links

Organisation/initiative name	Contact details
Nfdi e.V. (consider using de-RSE.org as proxy, maybe de-RSE.org will become a member of NFDI)	https://www.nfdi.de/en-gb

- What 2021 events would be a good location for FAIR4RS principles consultation?

Event name	+upvoters

- What types of materials would be helpful to facilitate discussions about FAIR 4 Research Software, other than the draft FAIR4RS principles?

Materials	Contributor +upvoters

Feedback

Thanks for joining us!!!

Let us know your thoughts of this session, we are looking to improve.

1. Did we meet your expectations?

Stephan Janosch (SJ): Yes

2. Did you feel comfortable during the workshop?

SJ: Yes

3. What was the most memorable thing from your experience with us?

SJ: The thought - "Why now?"

4. Is there anything else you would like us to know about your experience?

5. What can be improved for the next session?

SJ: The big picture could have been framed better. E.g. a very rough timeline over the last 30 years (www invented, first software journal, first RSE conf, first publisher demanding software references).

SJ: Go for the breakout rooms. Maybe spending more time on one topic is more productive, incl. getting a summary of the other breakout rooms. The first 2 hours felt smooth and clam, the last hour just flew by. It became a bit hectic. I had the feeling, not being able to think long enough about the questions.